

ANALYSIS OF THE ETHICAL CULTURE OF THE NEW GENERATION OF MANAGERS AND THE FACTORS INFLUENCING IT

Tajiboev Sarvar

Fergana State University

PhD student of the Department of Philosophy

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Abstract: The article analyzes the perspective of the strategy of New Uzbekistan and the considerations related to the institution of democratic management. Also, management is scientifically based on the principle of commitment to democracy and social justice. Because the state carries out its activities based on the principles of social justice and legality, aiming at the well-being of people and society. Also, governance as a political institution is based on pluralism. This is especially true in a democratic society. Therefore, the purpose of management in the new Uzbekistan is set at the constitutional level as "creating the well-being of man and society". Its basis is three: democracy, social justice and legality. These three concepts, in turn, form the basis of the responsibilities of management personnel.

Key words: democratic management, moral culture of personnel, leadership ability, subordinates' activity, administrative command.

1. It is difficult to imagine a management system without decisions, orders, instructions, and orders. However, the bureaucratic leader forgets that these documents are programs for daily activities and sees everything from the point of view of a template. However, all the various problems that arise in life due to various reasons do not always correspond to the standards set in these instructions, in other words, the regulatory documents cannot reflect all the situations that a leader may encounter during his work. In such situations, courage, ability to take responsibility, ability to work independently, initiative qualities are required from the leader. A bureaucratic leader is not capable of this. He does not have the ability to take full responsibility and approach the problem creatively. Therefore, even where a private solution is needed, he clings to a general demand, or looks for a reason for his inaction, for doing nothing, from layers of documents.

2. But neither the citizen nor the state benefits from such an approach. As a result of this, the existing problem remains unsolved. The bureaucratic leader says, "I solved the problem to the best of my ability." But imagine, as a result of such an approach, an applicant whose concerns are not resolved at the district level will rush to the region. In the region, if the application falls into the hands of a sane official, then a will will be created. Otherwise, he wanders back to the capital. In this way, the collective economy or the relevant will in the district should be resolved, and the possible problem reaches the central offices in the capital. In such a situation, one or two bureaucrats appear due to the cold attitude of the leader to his duties.

3. At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, the work of training new modern management personnel requires a scientific approach, taking into account the objective situation. The process of training management personnel in Uzbekistan has a programmatic basis, and it consists of a continuous system of a number of activities, such as the selection of

students who have the ability to lead, improving their knowledge, and forming their professional skills.

4. Several steps can be distinguished:

5. First of all, it should be said that a person entrusted with the management of any field must have the necessary professional knowledge and skills, be an expert in this field.

6. Forming an ideal leader model based on the personal and professional requirements of Uzbekistan's development for leaders, applying it in the process of training and retraining leaders. In other words, the art of leadership is the development of norms and rules.

7. Finding young, promising professionals with leadership skills, teaching them leadership culture and improving leadership skills.

8. Constantly improve the mechanisms of training of managerial personnel, for this purpose analyze the effectiveness of the process of training of managerial personnel.

9. To put the leading personnel in place and regularly pass them through attestation.

10. Determination of new technological goals and tasks based on current requirements of personnel policy in accordance with the development, growth and changes taking place in the state and society. Thus, specific criteria have been developed in Uzbekistan for the training of modern managers and they are being put into practice. These criteria are consistent with modern management methods and democratic principles of leadership.

The moral qualities and talent of management personnel are manifested in the performance of the following 19 tasks: 1) organizing the activities of subordinates; 2) work planning; 3) decision-making; 4) being able to receive information from "above"; 5) being able to get information from the "bottom"; 6) recognition of performers; 7) ability to make demands on subordinates; 8) intellectually guide subordinates' activities; 9) increase the efficiency of subordinates' activities; 10) ability to treat subordinates moderately; 11) ability to cooperate with subordinates; 12) educating subordinates; 13) ability to deal with subordinates; 14) application of punitive measures; 15) use of incentives; 16) self-control; 17) work on oneself; 18) being able to be critical of one's own work; 19) to be able to evaluate one's own activity [1]. Among these, one can add the quality of understanding the demands of the times.

At this point, it should be noted that the leader's talent is demonstrated by fulfilling these requirements and tasks. Because the question is how to do them.

A leader must be inquisitive to improve his professional and spiritual consciousness. Striving for innovation, ability to accept innovation and create innovation determines the level of moral responsibility of the leader. Because a leader who does not strive for innovation will live with yesterday and today, tomorrow (future) will be lost in his activity.

Depending on the searchability of leaders, they can be divided into three groups: 1) positive types - they create a good atmosphere in the team; 2) negative types - create a bad atmosphere in the team; 3) intermediate types - create an uncertain environment in the team[2]. The purpose of this is to emphasize that an aspiring leader is characterized by a sense of responsibility towards the team (subordinates). In addition, searchability remains the main criterion that determines the level of spiritual leadership.

Today's leader is required to be aware of economics, information technology, law, politics and spirituality. Because we have new economic relations (economy), cooperation with the enlightened world (information technology), national statehood (law), new society

(politics) and the formation and establishment of a new personality (spirituality). This represents the content of modern education. Therefore, modern education is a deep study of the knowledge that is suitable for the needs of the time and solving the existing problems.

In addition to deep knowledge of his specialty, the leader must master the art of management. In this regard, he must be an example to others by knowing his profession, understanding the times and being socially active.

The leader should have his own word, opinion and view on every issue. In a certain issue, he should speak the word he understands, express the opinion he understands, and say his opinion on the solution of the issue. It is necessary to refrain from parroting general sentences consisting of true and false conclusions. Indolence, laziness in people has a great impact on the labor process, as a result of which some people advance, and the other part lags behind. This also causes new problems for managers. Achieving the final result of socio-economic reforms in places, bringing the started work to an end, forming a new worldview in people, constitute the core of the tasks before us.

The presence of leaders with old ways of thinking and old ways of thinking was not noticed at the beginning of the reforms, as the reforms deepened and social views in the society moved towards renewal, the need for a new worldview to manage people began to be felt. Thus, the introduction of modern management methods takes place as a means of increasing the moral responsibility of managers. The following successes can be achieved if the moral responsibility of enterprise leaders, in general, is increased:

1. To democratize management methods on the basis of legality;
2. Introduction of team management instead of administrative command management in enterprises.
3. To increase the moral responsibility of leading employees in management. After all, all this work requires constant updates.

In addition to the ordinary everyday concept of goodness, there is also a definition of it as a category of the science of ethics. For example, A.A. Radugin said, "Goodness is something that is considered very necessary and useful for society and individual life. Goodness is all that is necessary for the existence, development, well-being, harmony and perfection of society and the individual"[3], A.A. Guseynov and R.G. Apresyan "Goodness is on the one hand pleasing and useful to a person, on the one hand and if there is a work that is valued for others, on the other hand, the work that is valuable for oneself and not for others is behavior"[4] . N.E.Muhammadyev "Goodness is the sum of all the positive aspects of all the events, events and things that happen around us that honor a person, satisfy his interests and needs, provide the growth of humanity in accordance with moral ideals, and ultimately serve to lead a happy life. it is said" [5] , defines it as.

Today, some of our leaders lack the ability to see strategic goals. They cannot imagine the future of the industry they lead. If you look at their activities, you can see that they are only focused on today's tasks. To be a true leader, a leader must work transparently, democratically, and trusting others. A strong leader can listen to the advice of others and become a leader that no one else can interfere with. As a result, tomorrow's problems can be prevented today. An enterprising leader burns, lives and works with pleasure. The initiative of the leader is known in three things: uniting people, leading them and mobilizing them. Where there is no unity, there is no blessing and no fruitfulness. When management (organization) is weak, order undermines discipline. Without mobilization, there is no creativity.

In conclusion, the personal qualities and qualities of management personnel are formed in the space and time in which they lived and were educated. In the current new era, there are great opportunities for the rapid formation of high moral qualities in the leadership staff. The changing social environment, work style, management style, requirements created the objective conditions necessary for the education of new types of state officials and leading personnel. The main task of Gal is to scientifically base, analyze, generalize the new demands placed on management personnel, the necessary qualities for them, and specially form them with the help of spiritual and educational education and practical experience. That's when the renewal of the thinking of management personnel will reach the people, that is, every Uzbek. The thinking of the society will be updated faster, the nation will become one soul and one body, and the reforms will accelerate.

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